

A Study on Occupational Stress Management Among Nurses in Rajaji Government Hospital, Madurai

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Abstract

This paper is concerned with an occupational stress management among nurses in Rajaji Government Hospital, Madurai. The study is based on the systematic method of data collection and analysis. The primary data are collected from 100 sample respondents of Government Rajaji hospital. A complete survey has been under taken in all the selected nurses. The DASS Scale was used to study the stress on work related activities, relations with co-worker, educational qualification, workload and age. The results indicated that there is a significant difference in all the emotional conditions and the stress level was higher among the co-workers than other related variables. The study found out that indicated the women nurses face many problems due to the conflict between their domestic commitments and workplace demands. The study suggests that nurses should take a fresh look at their personal and professional goals and devise ways to balance them. The hospitals and government should come up with policies and programs to protect the interests of the nurses.

Keyword: Occupational Stress, Nurses, Management, Hospital, etc.,

Introduction

"Health is Wealth," Health is considered as the most important phenomenon in today's world which determines the wealth of the country at large. The health care industry in India is one of the largest economic and fastest growing professions. In order to create a balance between the provision and reception of health care various strategies have been worked out which makes the industry effectively by health consciousness among people and welfare schemes. The health indicators of the population in India bring forth the graveness of the health human resource shortage existing in the country. A comparison of health indicators of India with other developing

countries shows that the mortality levels experienced in India remain quite high. The disparities in health status in India can be observed across the rural-urban regions and amongst the states. The differences in health status of the population of India reflect in part the disparities in terms of the availability and accessibility of health services. In order to improve the health services women nurses play an important role than Doctors. The nursing profession in India lacks high professional status, has low and unattractive salaries, gets inadequate recognition from the community for the services provided by them and has little incentives for quality performance.

Significance of the Study

A nurse is a healthcare professional who along with other health care. They are responsible for the treatment, safety, and recovery of acute or chronic ill or injured people, health maintenance of the unhealthy people and treatment of life-threatening emergencies in a wide range of health care settings. Nursing requires gentleness, compassion and sensitivity. Even though the largest group of workers in the health sector, nursing occupations play an important role. In a hospital from the general ward to the operating theatre, nursing forms an integral part. In the government hospital at the initial level, nurses are required for the bedside care of patients, while at senior level they are required to manage special group of people like psychiatric, pediatric, intensive care patients etc., which require specialized skills. They are also involved in dispensing medication, keeping records of the patients' progress, setting up and operating medical equipment, administration and several other routine chores than doctors. Nurses want safe workplaces that promote quality health care for the patient. "Nurses want to work in a place that brings high quality care to patients and know they have a role in the process. Based on the above problem, the researchers aimed at investigate about the job stress of the nurses of Madurai Rajaji Hospital and specifically to assess the anxiety of nurses, identify factors associated with job satisfaction.

Problem of the Study

Stress in nurses is an unavoidable problem. It contributes to health problems of nurses in different dimension. Documenting the causes and management of stress in any healthcare unit is essential for successful interventions. The problem of this study therefore, is to investigate how job related stress affect the physical and mental health, personal work behavior of nurses in Madurai government Rajaji Hospital. This field is both mentally as well as and physically affected in nature. Nurses are often exposed to health risks from infectious diseases. As such this profession demands long hours of work and duties which incorporate both skill and understanding of patients needs. Those who come forward to take up this as a career has to be patient, courageous, have a service mentality and at the same time be ready to work for extra hours even night shifts.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study is to analyse the types of stress among the nurses in Government Rajaji Hospital Madurai, to find out about the sources of stress among nurses and control group in Government Rajaji Hospital Madurai and to make valuable suggestion regarding nurse stress.

Mehodology

The research is based on the systematic method of data collection and analysis. Primary data are used for this study. The primary data are collected from 100 sample respondents of Government Rajaji Hospital.

Tools

Questionnaire was the main tool used to collect the pertinent data from the selected sample respondents. For this purpose, a well structured questionnaire was framed with the help of chief Executive Officer (CEO), Head Nurse, Nursing Superintendent/Matron, Supervisors.

The study was conducted on the nurses at different units in Madurai Rajaji Government Hospital. The general units were Medical ward, Surgical ward, Pediatric, Heart, Orthopedic, Gynecology, Emergency ward, Nephrology, Neurology, Neurosurgery, ENT, Eye, CCU ward, ICU ward, Maternity (New Born), Delivery room, Operating room, Skin. The DASS Scale was used to study the stress on work related activities, relations with co-worker, educational qualification, workload and age.

Analysis

The test included 75 questions and response to test a range of 6 degree. The result of the test is explained with the following prescribed objectives. To find out the sources of stress among nurses in Madurai Government Rajaji Hospital.

The aim of this hypothesis is to find out the stress among 6 important concept of the Nurses in the hospital.

Table 1 Relationship Between Gender and Stress (Chi Square Test)

Variables	Pearsons Chi Square Test(X ²)	Types of Stress Experienced		
		Physical	Emotional	Psychological
Gender	X ²	0.463	0.471	0.493
	P Value	P > 0.05	P > 0.05	P > 0.05
	Remarks	No Significant Difference	No Significant Difference	No Significant Difference

Hypothesis 1: There is no statistically significant relationship between Gender of nurses and the stress. Table 1 reveals that the calculated Pearson's Chi-square for the physical, emotional and psychological types of stress experienced are (0.463, 0.471, 0.493) (P>0.05) respectively. The value of Pearson's chi-square represent a relationship not significantly different from zero (P>0.05) in favour of the null hypothesis. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no statistically significant relationship between the sex of nurses and the types of occupational stress experienced by nurses.

Table 2 Relationship Between Education and Stress (Chi Square Test)

Variables	Pearsons Chi Square Test(X ²)	Types of Stress Experienced		
		Physical	Emotional	Psychological
Education	X ²	0.001	0.000	0.632
	P Value	P > 0.05	P > 0.05	P > 0.05
	Remarks	No Significant Difference	No Significant Difference	No Significant Difference

Hypothesis 2: There is no statistically significant relationship between Education of nurses and stress. Table 2 reveals that the calculated Pearson's Chi-square for the physical and psychological types of stress experienced are (0.001, 0.000, 0.632) (P>0.05) and the calculated Pearson's Chi-square for the emotional types of stress experienced is 0.00 (P0.05) respectively. The value of Pearson's chi-square represent a relationship not significantly different from zero (P>0.05) in favour of the null hypothesis. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no statistically

significant relationship between the education and the types of occupational stress experienced by nurses.

The study shows that there is a relationship between education and stress. If there is more education stress relief is less. There is a positive association between education and job stress.

Work Load

As per this study, unpredictable schedule and workload is the major problem faced by the women nurses in Madurai Government Rajaji Hospital. Nurses in supervisory positions, who make patient care assignments, need to be sensitive to the workload involved with each assignment and the schedule should be informed well in advance. It will be helpful to enhance the job satisfaction. It has been observed that workload is the main stress among nurses. Because they have faces many problems throughout the day. Not only that the hospital is located in the congested area and the number of patients refer the hospital often like accident case and same emergency cases. The study found out that the stress is high for the superior and ward nurses.

Table 3 Relationship Between Workload and Stress (Chi Square Test)

Variables	Pearsons Chi Square Test(X2)	Types of Stress Experienced		
		Physical	Emotional	Psychological
Workload	X2	0.001	0.002	0.469
	P Value	P > 0.05	P > 0.05	P > 0.05
	Remarks	No Significant Difference	No Significant Difference	No Significant Difference

Hypothesis 3: There is no statistically significant relationship between workload or work environment of nurses and the stress. Table 3 reveals that the calculated Pearson's Chi-square for the physical, emotional and psychological types of stress experienced are (0.01, 0.02, 0.469) (P>0.05) respectively. The value of Pearson's chi-square represent a relationship not significantly different from zero (P>0.05) in favour of the null hypothesis. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no statistically significant relationship between the salaries earned by nurses and the types of occupational stress experienced by nurses.

Ranking

Table 4 Relationship Between Ranking and Stress (Chi Square Test)

Variables	Pearsons Chi Square Test(X2)	Types of Stress Experienced		
		Physical	Emotional	Psychological
Ranking	X2	0.001	0.001	0.110
	P Value	P > 0.05	P > 0.05	P > 0.05
	Remarks	No Significant Difference	No Significant Difference	No Significant Difference

Hypothesis 4: There is no statistically significant relationship between ranking or work environment of nurses and the stress. Table 4 reveals that the calculated Pearson's Chi-square for the physical, emotional and psychological types of stress experienced are (0.01, 0.01, 0.110) (P>0.05) respectively. The value of Pearson's chi-square represent a relationship not significantly different from zero (P>0.05) in favour of the null hypothesis. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no statistically significant relationship between the salaries earned by nurses and the types of occupational stress experienced by nurses.

Findings and Suggestions

The results of this study highlighted the need to restore the state of physical and psychological health of the nurses who work primarily in care activities in open units, and with adult patients. Finally, the aspects considered in the present study are elements that can contribute to the conception and development of measures aimed at preserving the work capacity, prioritizing the monitoring and control of occupational stress with emphasis on the psychological work relationships, thus, improving the promotion, the protection and the restoration of the health of the workers. This study aimed at finding out the Nature of work, Supervisors, Co-workers, income, autonomy, which are related to make stress among the nurses in Madurai Rajaji Government. The results indicated that there is a significant difference in all the emotional conditions and the stress level was higher among the co-workers than other related variables. Job stress is negatively associated with increased symptoms of ill-health.

Suggestion and Recommendations

To ensure that efficient nursing care is given to the patients, the government (Federal, State) the Ministries of Health or the hospital management boards should help in reducing sources of stress in the nurses. Their working conditions need to be quickly improved by giving them adequate recognition that commensurate with the demands of their jobs. Their promotion should be done as at when due to boost their morale. They should also be involved in vital decisions concerning their jobs and their patients. In service training, workshops and seminars should be organized for nurses to update their knowledge and skill. They should be sent for courses on human behavior, resource management, interpersonal relation, stress management and crisis interventions.

Conclusion

The type of stress experienced by majority of the nurses revealed that inadequate leadership and dominating characters of superior. With regard to causes of stress identified more night shift handling a large number of patients lack of incentives, lack of promotion, nursing difficult patients and harassment from patients. Most of them identified job insecurity is the major cause of stress. In conclusion, health care professionals are more susceptible to occupational stress because of intense daily activity. Nurse are not ever thought of as needing help but only as the care givers, and applying some techniques for nursing stress burnout prevention are more important than we ever thought. In seeking to identify which stress management activities work the best, it is advisable to try a number of different strategies especially the healthy ones and then determine which ones seem to be the most effective. It is hoped that when nurses are given adequate support by their employers they can work more. Their needs will experience less aggressive or hostile to the patients or their families. The patients will also receive better and adequate nursing care from them.

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